

Design, Fabrication, and In Vitro Evaluation of Nanoceria-Loaded Nanostructured Lipid Carriers for the Treatment of Neurological Diseases

Matteo Battaglini,^{*,†,‡} Christos Tapeinos,^{*,†} Ivana Cavaliere,[§] Attilio Marino,[†] Andrea Ancona,^{||} Nadia Garino,^{||,⊥} Valentina Cauda,^{||,⊥} Francisco Palazon,[#] Doriana Debellis,[¶] and Gianni Ciofani^{*,†,§,Ⓢ}

[†]Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Smart Bio-Interfaces, Viale Rinaldo Piaggio 34, 56025 Pontedera, Pisa, Italy

[‡]Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, The Biorobotics Institute, Viale Rinaldo Piaggio 34, 56025 Pontedera, Pisa, Italy

[§]Politecnico di Torino, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy

^{||}Politecnico di Torino, Department of Applied Science and Technology, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy

[⊥]Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Center for Sustainable Future Technologies, Corso Trento 21, 10129 Torino, Italy

[#]Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Nanochemistry, Via Morego 30, 16163 Genova, Italy

[¶]Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Electron Microscopy Facility, Via Morego 30, 16163 Genova, Italy

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Neurodegenerative diseases comprise a large group of disorders characterized by a dramatic synaptic connections loss, occurring as a result of neurodegeneration, which is closely related to the overproduction of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species. Currently, the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases has been limited mainly because of the inability of the synthesized delivery systems to cross the blood-brain barrier and to successfully deliver their therapeutic cargo to the diseased tissue. Taking into consideration the aforementioned limitations, we designed a lipid-based nanotherapeutic vector composed of biomimetic lipids and CeO₂ nanoparticles (nanoceria, NC). NC have shown to be a promising tool for the treatment of several pathological conditions ranging from cancer to neurological diseases, mainly because of their antioxidant properties, while lipid-based structures have been shown to have an inherent ability to cross the blood-brain barrier. The lipid-based nanotherapeutics were successfully fabricated using a combination of ultrasonication and high-pressure homogenization techniques, and they were fully characterized morphologically and physicochemically. Their antioxidant ability was demonstrated using electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy and antioxidant assays. These innovative nanotherapeutics demonstrated a higher colloidal stability with respect to free NC, preserving at the same time their antioxidant properties. Finally, the ability of the lipid carriers to cross a model of the blood-brain barrier and to be internalized by neurons, acting both as neuroprotective and pro-neurogenic agents, was demonstrated using single- and triple-culture systems.

KEYWORDS: cerium oxide nanoparticles, antioxidants, blood-brain barrier, nanostructured lipid carriers

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, CeO₂ nanoparticles (nanoceria, NC) have gained the attention of the research community as a potential therapeutic agent for the treatment of several pathological conditions, including Alzheimer's disease,¹ Parkinson's disease,² stroke,³ and different forms of cancer.^{4,5} This is mainly due to the NC unique characteristics that distinguish them from other antioxidant compounds. NC have in fact several advantages over other reactive oxygen species (ROS) scavenging substances, like the possibility to act on a broad spectrum of different ROS including hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), and the superoxide anion (O²⁻).⁶

In addition, NC are able to self-regenerate thanks to the continuous redox cycle that involves Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ cations on their surface, granting NC the possibility to act as "virtually endless" antioxidant agents, even after a single administration.⁶ Despite their advantages, the exploitation of NC in biomedical applications has raised several concerns regarding their true effectiveness and toxicity.⁷ In fact, while it has been widely shown that NC are not intrinsically toxic or harmful,⁸ it has

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also been described how their antioxidant properties could not only be “compromised”, but also be “inverted” (changing NC from antioxidant agents to pro-oxidant compounds) resulting in adverse effects. This inversion can be affected by several factors, including aggregation levels,⁹ interaction with proteins or other macromolecules,¹⁰ and exposure to low pH due to a specific subcellular localization.¹¹

In this work, we addressed these limitations by designing an innovative nanovector able to encapsulate NC (<5 nm) without affecting their antioxidant capacity, yet increasing their colloidal stability. Our formulation represents an exponent of the last generation of lipid vectors, the so-called nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), a subclass of lipid nanoparticles made of a solid lipid external layer with small drops of liquid oil dispersed throughout the inner lipid matrix.¹² NLCs have been largely studied thanks to their advantages over other nanostructured systems in terms of increased biocompatibility, stability, and loading efficiencies.¹³ We successfully fabricated and characterized NC-loaded NLCs (NC-NLCs) with a high loading efficiency (~30% w/w) and with an enhanced colloidal stability compared to free NC. The maintenance of NC antioxidant properties after encapsulation was confirmed both by analysis performed using electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy and by *in vitro* testing on neuroblastoma-derived neurons (differentiated SH-SY5Y) subjected to a pro-oxidative treatment. Moreover, we have also preliminarily investigated the possibility to use these innovative nanostructures in the treatment of neurological diseases. Briefly, although brain diseases are very heterogeneous and each of them is characterized by its own hallmarks, most of them (including the five most common that are Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, brain cancer, ischemic stroke, and multiple sclerosis¹⁴) share two common characteristics: a high level of oxidative stress and a progressive loss of neuronal processes and neurons.¹⁴ The treatment of these diseases is further hampered by the presence of the blood-brain barrier (BBB), a continuous membrane mainly constituted by brain endothelial cells, astrocytes, and pericytes, that envelopes the central nervous system, forming an obstacle to the passage of noxious substances, drugs, and other therapeutic molecules.¹⁵ In order to test the ability of NC-NLCs to cross the BBB and to be exploited as a neuro-therapeutic agent, we designed an *in vitro* BBB triple-culture model, consisting of brain endothelial cells (bEnd.3), astrocytes (C8-D1A), and neurons (differentiated SH-SY5Y). NC-NLCs showed the ability to cross the endothelial cells/astrocytes bilayer and to be internalized by neurons in a concentration high enough to elicit their antioxidant functions. Finally, NC-NLCs showed also the ability to stimulate neuronal differentiation in terms of average number and length of neurites. These results lay the foundations for the exploitation of NC-NLCs in a broad range of different and exciting therapeutic applications.

■ EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Preparation of Nanoceria-Loaded Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NC-NLCs). NC-NLCs were fabricated using a combination of ultrasonication and high-pressure homogenization. Briefly, 10 mg of NC (<5 nm, Alfa Aesar) were mixed with 2.5 mg of commercial olive oil, 25 mg of cetyl palmitate (CP, Gattefossé), and 4 mg of 1,2-distearoyl-*sn*-glycerol-3-phosphoethanolamine-conjugated poly-(ethylene glycol) (mPEG-DSPE, 5000 Da, Nanocs Inc.), and then the mixture was left at 60 °C for 10 min. After the complete melting of the solid lipid phase, a preheated (60 °C) water solution of Pluronic F127 (10 mg/mL, Sigma, a stabilizing agent) was added to

the lipid mixture and sonicated for 5 min at 8 W using a Bandelin ultrasonic probe. After the sonication, the obtained oil-in-water emulsion was pumped inside a high-pressure homogenizer (HPH) and homogenized 5 times at 30 000 psi homogenizing pressure. FITC-labeled NC-NLCs were also fabricated by replacing 1 mg of mPEG-DSPE with 1 mg of fluorescein isothiocyanate-conjugated DSPE-PEG (DSPE-PEG-FITC, Nanocs Inc.). The product of the homogenization was left to stabilize for 30 min at 4 °C. To clean nonencapsulated NC, unbound mPEG-DSPE, and small amorphous lipidic aggregates, the NC-NLCs were filtered using a 0.2 μm syringe filter and cleaned using Amicon Ultra Centrifugal Filters (cutoff of 100 kDa). The samples were centrifuged 3 times and the collected precipitate was redispersed in deionized water. The spinning speed was set at 7500g (8230 rpm), and the time was set to 20–45 min depending on the volume of the added water.

Dynamic Light Scattering. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements were performed using a Zetasizer NanoZS90 from Malvern instruments Ltd. NC-NLCs and free NC stability were measured at different time points and in different solvents including water, phosphate buffer saline (PBS 1×), and Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM), with and without fetal bovine serum (FBS, 10%). Before each measurement, the samples were sonicated for ~10 s using a Bandelin ultrasonic probe at 8 W, to avoid the presence of aggregates during measurements. The zeta potential measurements represent the mean ± SD of 3 different measurements with 17 runs in each measurement. DLS was also used for the degradation studies using PBS at pH 7.4 and at pH 4.5, with and without the use of 100 μM H₂O₂. The studies were carried out at 37 °C for 3 days, and in order to measure the hydrodynamic diameter, an aliquot (12.5 μL) of the stock solution was diluted in water (987.5 μL), and measured using the aforementioned conditions but with at least 6 measurements for each sample. The final concentration for the DLS measurements was adjusted to 100 μg/mL.

Electron Microscopy and Elemental Analysis. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analyses were performed using a JEOL 1011 transmission electron microscope operated at 100 kV with single-tilt holder. The samples were sonicated for 5 min before a drop of the sample solution was placed on a Cu grid, 150 mesh, coated with ultrathin amorphous carbon film. Before sample deposition, each grid was plasma-treated (O₂ + Ar plasma, 10 W, 2 min) in order to remove hydrocarbon residues from carbon film deposition. In order to enhance the contrast of lipid particles, the previously prepared sample grids were treated for 30 s with a 1% uranyl acetate solution in water. Annular dark-field (ADF) scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) was performed using a JEOL JEM-1400Plus transmission electron microscope with a LaB₆ thermionic source, operated at 120 kV using a double-tilt analytical holder. Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDS) analyses have been acquired using a JEOL Dry SD30GV silicon-drift detector (SDD), with 30 mm² effective area.

Atomic Force Microscopy. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) scans were performed in tapping mode by using a Veeco Bruker DiInnova Innova SPM Scanning Probe Microscope equipped with NT-MDT NSG01 antimony-doped n-type silicon probes, with a resonance frequency of 87–230 kHz and a force constant of 1.45–15.10 N/m⁻¹. Scans were carried out with a total of 1024 lines for sample and a scan frequency of 0.3 Hz. All data scans were elaborated and analyzed with the Gwyddion SPM analysis tool (<http://gwyddion.net>).

Fourier-Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy. Infrared spectroscopy was performed using a Shimadzu Miracle 10 spectrometer. Before the measurements, all the samples have been freeze-dried. The number of scans was set to 45, the scanning range was set from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ and the resolution step at 4 cm⁻¹. The graphs were plotted using Originpro software 9.1.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed on a Kratos Axis Ultra DLD spectrometer, using a monochromatic Al K α source operated at 15 kV and 20 mA. Specimens were prepared by pressing a few milligrams of the sample onto indium pellets. Wide scans were acquired at an analyzer pass energy of 160 eV, while high-resolution

narrow scans were performed at a constant pass energy of 10 eV and steps of 0.1 eV. The photoelectrons were detected at a takeoff angle $\varphi = 0^\circ$ with respect to the surface normal. The pressure in the analysis chamber was maintained below 5×10^{-9} Torr for data acquisition. The data were converted to VAMAS format and processed using CasaXPS software, version 2.3.17. Quantitative analysis was obtained by calculating the areas under the XPS peaks of the elements of interest, after normalization to the corresponding relative sensitivity factors (RSF), i.e., keeping into consideration the different cross sections for the photoemission process.

Thermogravimetric Analysis. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed on small samples (5 mg) using a Q500 analyzer from TA Instruments. The scans were performed in the range of 30–600 °C by using a 50 mL/min nitrogen flow, a 10 °C/min heating rate, and platinum pans.

Electron Paramagnetic Resonance Spectroscopy. The antioxidant activity of the nanoparticles was studied using electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy coupled with the spin-trapping technique. Hydroxyl radicals were generated in situ by Fenton reactions and trapped using the spin-trap 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline N-oxide (DMPO, Sigma). Briefly, H_2O_2 (20 μL , 10 mM), DMPO (100 μL , 50 mM), an aqueous solution of nanoparticles at different concentrations (78 μL), and FeSO_4 (2 μL , 10 mM) were mixed in an Eppendorf tube. The resulting solution was mixed, transferred into a 50 μL quartz microcapillary tube, and placed in the EPR cavity for measurement. The spectra were recorded on a Bruker EMXnano X-Band spectrometer (Bruker). The EPR measurement conditions were as follows: frequency 9.74 GHz, scan width 100 G, receiver gain 60 dB, time constant 1.28 ms, sweep time 80 s, scan 1. After the acquisition, the spectra were processed using the Bruker Xenon software (Bruker) for baseline correction, and the total number of trapped hydroxyl radicals was quantified using the SpinFit software (Bruker).

Cell Lines. In this study, three different cell lines were used, the mouse brain endothelial cell line bEnd.3 (ATCC CRL-2299), C8-D1A mouse type-I astrocytes (ATCC CRL2541), and the human neuroblastoma cell line SH-SY5Y (ATCC CRL-2266). bEnd.3 and C8-D1A were cultured in 10 cm diameter Petri dishes using high-glucose DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS (Sigma), 100 U/ml penicillin (Sigma), and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin (Sigma), at normal culture conditions (37 °C, 5% CO_2). SH-SY5Y cells were cultured both in proliferation medium consisting of DMEM/Ham's F12 1:1 supplemented with 10% FBS, 100 U/ml penicillin, and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin, and in differentiation medium comprising high-glucose DMEM supplemented with 1% FBS, 100 U/ml penicillin, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin, and 10 μM all-trans-retinoic acid (RA, Sigma). For all the experiments, the used cells were between passage 15 and passage 30. The medium during culture was changed every 2 days.

Cell Proliferation Analysis and Staining Procedures. Upon 80% of confluence in a 10 cm diameter Petri dish, both C8-D1A and bEnd.3 cell lines were detached using trypsin 0.05% and seeded at a density of 25×10^3 cells/ cm^2 in a 48-well tissue culture plate, with 200 μL of the same medium used for the culturing. After 24 h, the cells were treated with 100 and 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of NC, and with an equivalent concentration of NLCs and NC-NLCs (333 and 666 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). SH-SY5Y were seeded at a density of 25×10^3 cells/ cm^2 in a 24-well plate and differentiated for 6 days using the differentiation medium as previously mentioned. SH-SY5Y were treated in the same way as previously described for the other two cell lines.

Quantification of DNA, as an indication of cell proliferation, was performed using a PicoGreen dsDNA quantitation assay (ThermoFisher Inc.). Briefly, 200 μL of Milli-Q ultrapure water was added to the seeded cells, that were subsequently scrapped. The cell dispersion was frozen at -80 °C and after three freeze–thaw cycles a predetermined amount of the dispersion was used for DNA quantification. Sample fluorescence was measured using a PerkinElmer (Victor 2030) plate reader at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 480$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 520$ nm.

For imaging, cells were seeded in 24-well Ibidi μ -Plates and treated with different nanoformulations as previously described. Expression of specific proteins was evaluated through immunocytochemistry.

Briefly, after cell fixation (4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 20 min at 4 °C), membrane permeabilization (Triton X-100 in 0.1% in PBS for 25 min at room temperature), and treatment with blocking solution (10% goat serum in PBS for 1 h), cultures were incubated with primary rabbit IgG anti-ZO-1 antibody (Invitrogen, 1:200 in 10% goat serum for 3 h at room temperature (RT)) or with primary rabbit IgG anti- β 3 tubulin antibody (Sigma, 1:200 in 10% goat serum for 3 h at RT). Subsequently, cells were rinsed 5 times with 10% goat serum in PBS and then incubated with a staining solution of 10% goat serum in PBS containing TRITC-conjugated phalloidin (100 μM , Millipore), Hoechst 33342 (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, Invitrogen), and the secondary antibody (F(ab')₂-goat antirabbit IgG (H+L), Alexa Fluor 488 conjugate, Invitrogen). For intracellular localization of NC-NLCs, the cells were pretreated with FITC-NC-NLCs for 72 h and subsequently washed twice and stained with LysoTracker (75 nM, Invitrogen) and Hoechst 33342 (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, Invitrogen) in serum-free DMEM at 37 °C. Cells were then fixed as previously described and stained with Alexa Fluor 647 phalloidin (100 μM , Millipore). Imaging was performed using a confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM; C2s system, Nikon).

Establishment and Characterization of an In Vitro BBB Model. In order to set up the BBB in vitro model to assess the ability of NC-NLCs to cross the barrier, a triple-culture system of the aforementioned cell lines on transwell inserts was performed. At a first step, 12-well Corning transwell inserts with 0.4 μm pore size placed on 12-well plates were flipped down, and C8-D1A cells were seeded on the bottom side of the porous membrane, with a cell density of 5×10^4 cells/ cm^2 in a drop volume of 200 μL . After 6 h, the insets were flipped back up and bEnd.3 cells were seeded on the apical side of the membrane at the same cell density as the C8-D1A cells. After 3 days of growth, the insets were transferred in another 12-well plate (Corning) that was previously seeded with SH-SY5Y (5×10^4 cells/ cm^2), and that previously underwent 3 days of differentiation. Five days after the seeding of C8-D1A, the triple-culture system was characterized and exploited for permeability studies. Bioelectrical properties of the cell bilayer (C8-D1A and bEnd.3) were checked by measuring the transendothelial electrical resistance (TEER), using a MILLICELL-ERS 2 electrical resistance system (Merck Millipore) coupled with MERSSTX01 MILLICELL Electrodes. Morphological properties and protein expression of the cell bilayer were assessed by immunocytochemistry performed as previously mentioned. BBB integrity was studied by measuring the permeability of FITC-dextran (Thermo Fisher) of low (4 kDa) and high (70 kDa) molecular weight at different time points.

Internalization and BBB Crossing Studies. To calculate the amount of NLCs able to cross the BBB in vitro model, different concentrations of FITC-NC-NLCs (0.65, 1.3, and 2.6 mg/mL) were dispersed in the cell culture medium in the apical side of the transwell triple-culture system. After 24 and 72 h, 100 μL of cell culture media were taken from the basal compartment of the transwell and measured using a plate reader (Victor 2030, PerkinElmer) at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 480$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 520$ nm. The results were compared with a calibration curve previously set up in order to calculate the exact amount of FITC-NC-NLCs able to cross the BBB. Internalization and crossing of FITC-NC-NLCs were checked also by confocal imaging (as previously described) and by flow cytometry analysis performed at different time points (24 and 72 h) using a Beckman Coulter Cytoflex system ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525 \pm 40$ nm).

Assessment of ROS Levels/Necrosis. SH-SY5Y cells were seeded in a 12-well plate (5×10^4 cells/ cm^2 cell density) and differentiated for 6 days. After the differentiation, the cells were treated with 333 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of NLCs, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ NC, or 333 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ NC-NLCs for 24 h, and then subjected to oxidative stimulation by using *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (TBH, 1 mM or 5 mM, Sigma) for 3 h. After the oxidative insult, the cells were trypsinized and incubated with CellROX (5 μM , Invitrogen) and propidium iodide (PI, 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, Sigma) for the assessment of ROS production and viability by flow cytometry. Briefly, cells were washed with Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DBSS) without calcium and magnesium and detached using trypsin-EDTA (0.05%). A total of 200×10^3 cells per tube were

Figure 1. Morphological characterization and elemental analysis of NC-NLCs. (a) TEM image of NC-NLCs stained with uranyl acetate showing heterogeneity in the size of lipid nanoparticles; (b) TEM image of an unstained sample showing the presence of electron-dense small particles associated with the surface of lipid structures; (c) ADF/STEM image of NC-NLCs; (d) and (e) elemental analysis of the area presented in image (c), underlying the presence of oxygen and cerium in areas occupied by the NC-NLCs; (f) EDS spectrum of elements present in NC-NLCs; (g) 3D rendering of an AFM scan showing the spherical morphology of a single NC-NLC.

stained with 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of PI for 15 min at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ protected from light. Cells stained with CellROX/PI were evaluated using the Beckman Coulter Cytoflex ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525 \pm 40 \text{ nm}$ for CellROX fluorescence and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 585 \pm 42 \text{ nm}$ for PI fluorescence). Viable cells (CellROX-, PI-), necrotic cells with high ROS-level (CellROX+, PI+), and necrotic cells with low level of ROS (CellROX-, PI+) were analyzed using Flowjo software (Flowjo LLC). Untreated cells were used as a control.

Neuronal Differentiation Studies. Neuronal differentiation studies were carried out on SH-SY5Y, after 3 days of incubation in differentiation medium, under different treatments (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ NC, 333 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ NLCs, or 333 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ NC-NLCs). Cells were stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue (Sigma) and by performing an immunostaining against $\beta 3$ -tubulin. Briefly, cells were fixed (4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 20 min at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and then washed two times with Milli-Q water. After the washes, the cells were stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue (0.2% in methanol and 10% acetic acid for 10 min) and then washed five times with Milli-Q water. Images were acquired both by confocal microscopy and bright field microscopy. The average ratio between neurites and cell number and the average length of the neuronal processes were measured using ImageJ software.

Statistical Analysis. The statistical analysis was carried out using R software. The normality of data distribution was tested using the Shapiro–Wilk normality test. For normal distributions, multiple parametric confrontations among data groups were performed using ANOVA followed by the HSD posthoc test. For non-normal distributions, the Kruskal–Wallis nonparametric test followed by pairwise Wilcoxon posthoc test was carried out. Non-normal

distributions of data were expressed as median $\pm 95\%$ confident interval and were shown in box-plots (the threshold for statistically significant difference was set at $p < 0.05$). For the analysis of colocalization between different fluorescent signals, we reported the Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) provided by NIS-elements analysis software (Nikon), and we considered values of $r < 0.4$ as indicative of the absence of correlation among data groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological Characterization and Elemental Analysis. NLCs were chosen as a carrier for NC encapsulation because of their better performance in terms of loading efficiency and stability compared to other lipid structures like solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs).¹³ The presented system represents an innovative approach for the fabrication of nanoantioxidant delivery systems because it comprises the first attempt described in the literature for the preparation of NC-loaded carriers totally composed of lipids, and with the only comparable work being a study performed by our group, where NC have been encapsulated inside liposomes.¹⁵ The choice of cetyl palmitate as the solid lipid and olive oil as the liquid lipid was made because of the low cost and high biocompatibility that these lipids present.^{14,16} In order to increase the biocompatibility and the colloidal stability of the fabricated system, as well as to add a stealth ability to the NC-NLCs, mPEG-DSPE was also used. This hybrid material was

Figure 2. Physicochemical characterization of the particles. (a) TGA analysis of NC (i and iii) and of NC-NLCs (ii and iv) presenting the weight loss (i and ii) and the derivative of the weight loss (ii and iv) in relation to temperature increment; (b) FTIR analysis showing spectra of NLCs (i), NC-NLCs (ii), and NC (iii); XPS spectrum of NC-NLCs in (c) wide scan and (d) high-resolution scan, where XPS analysis on the energy region typical for Ce 3d peaks is also reported, together with the result of the best-fit procedure; (e) short-term stability study presenting the average hydrodynamic diameter (R_d) of NC and of NC-NLCs in PBS and in DMEM, with and without FBS ($n = 3$, mean \pm SD).

chosen due to the dual hydrophilic (PEG segment) and hydrophobic (DSPE) nature that it presents. The lipid part of this compound is able to be mixed with the rest of the lipids (cetyl palmitate and olive oil) and thus to be part of the lipid matrix, while the hydrophilic part can remain outside the lipid nanostructure in contact with the aqueous solution. This PEG segment increases the colloidal stability and protects the lipid nanostructures from opsonization after intravenous administration. Finally, Pluronic F-127 creates a layer around the lipid nanostructure providing further structural stability and an enhanced protection against oxidation, as shown in previous studies^{17–19}

After the synthesis, morphological characterization has been performed through TEM, ADF STEM, and AFM imaging. From the TEM and ADF/STEM images (Figure 1a–c), we can appreciate that we were able to obtain spherical structures with a diameter in the range 100–200 nm, together with smaller structures of around 20 nm. Further, uranyl acetate staining of the NLCs enabled identification of smaller and larger spherical structures²⁰ (Figure 1a). The unstained

samples that are presented in Figure 1b revealed the presence of small (<5 nm) electron-dense structures on the surface and inside the NLCs that can be identified as NC. The elemental analysis and the elemental mapping that are presented in Figure 1d–f show the presence of cerium (Ce) and oxygen (O) on structures that can be identified in Figure 1c as NLCs, suggesting the encapsulation of NC inside the NLCs. Through AFM scanning performed in tapping mode (Figure 1g), we were able to further confirm the spherical morphology of our particles.

Physicochemical Characterization. In order to confirm the presence of the incorporated NC in the NLCs, we performed zeta potential analysis, TGA, FTIR, and XPS measurements. The zeta potential measurement showed a negative surface charge of plain NLCs (-16.2 ± 0.5 mV) while a shifting toward positive values was observed when NLCs were fabricated in the presence of NC ($+19.6 \pm 0.75$ mV), suggesting the presence of NC either in the lipid structures and on their outer surface.

Figure 3. •OH scavenging ability of NC, NLCs, and NC-NLCs. (a) Representative EPR spectra obtained after 5 min from the initiation of Fenton reaction: the characteristic four peaks of the DMPO–OH adduct are detected. Corresponding NPs concentrations: NLCs 3.332 mg/mL, NC 1.000 mg/mL, NC-NLCs 3.332 mg/mL; (b) •OH scavenging efficiency obtained for the three samples as a percentage of the number of radicals in the absence of nanoparticles (control experiment). The number of •OH detected by EPR was calculated from the EPR spectra using the SpinFit software (Bruker).

TGA was carried out to calculate the percentage of the encapsulated NC and to evaluate structural changes of the lipid nanoparticles in relation to temperature alterations. The weight loss curve of NC and NC-NLCs, as well as their corresponding differential thermogravimetric (DTG) spectra, are presented in Figure 2a. A small weight loss of about 10%, which can be attributed to moisture, can be observed in the temperature range of 30–200 °C. While temperature further increases, the samples lose the majority of their weight; for the free NC, a weight loss can be observed from approximately 250 to 350 °C, and it can be probably attributed to a polymer coating that is used to stabilize the commercial nanoceria. For the NC-NLCs, a weight loss is achieved in two steps, as it can also be observed from the differential thermal analysis graphs, where two endothermic peaks are presented. The first endothermic peak can be attributed to the degradation of the polymeric coating that covers nanoceria as we previously mentioned, while the second one can be attributed to the degradation of CP. Both of these temperatures (269 and 372 °C) are in agreement with data presented in the literature.²¹ Above 400 °C, it can be observed that there is no further weight loss due to the fact that both the polymeric and the lipid coating have been completely degraded. The remaining weight can be attributed to the encapsulated nanoceria and corresponds approximately to the 30% of the total initial weight.

To further verify the presence of NC in NC-NLCs, FT-IR analysis has been performed (Figure 2b). The peaks present in the range 2800–3000 cm^{-1} belong to the C–H stretching vibration of the aliphatic chain of the liquid and solid lipids, as well as of the mPEG-DSPE and Pluronic F127 aliphatic chains. Lower at the mid-infrared range, the peaks at 1750 and 850 cm^{-1} correspond to the C=O stretching vibrations of the cetyl palmitate, olive oil, and mPEG-DSPE, as well as to the C–C stretching vibration of the lipid mixture, of mPEG-DSPE, and of the surfactant, respectively. Although for nanoceria only the peak at 591 cm^{-1} that corresponds to Ce–O vibration should have been detected, other two peaks at 1480 and 1586 cm^{-1} are present, that can be attributed to the polymer coating present on the commercial nanoceria.

Continuing with physicochemical characterization, XPS analysis was used to assess the percentages of the elements that are present on the surface of the NC-NLCs. The spectra that are presented in Figure 2c,d show the presence of carbon

(81.0%), which is the main component of the lipid nanoparticles, as well as the presence of Ce (0.9%). Traces of In are also present because of exposed areas of the used substrate. High-resolution XPS analysis on the energy region typical for Ce 3d peaks is also reported, together with the result of the best-fit procedure after subtraction of a linear background. The fitting of the data followed a procedure previously described¹⁶ and allows to estimate a Ce(III)/Ce(IV) ratio of approx 1 in our sample.

In order to evaluate the colloidal stability of free NC and NC-NLCs, a short-term stability study was performed using dynamic light scattering. PBS (1×), plain DMEM without phenol red, as well as DMEM without phenol red and supplemented with 10% FBS (DMEM + 10% FBS) were used as dispersants, in order to simulate conditions of medium with a high ionic strength that can be found in human body fluids. The results that are presented in Figure 2e demonstrate a better stability trend of NC-NLCs compared with the free NC. More specifically, it is obvious that the hydrodynamic diameter of the NC-NLCs is relatively stable at approximately 125 nm when DMEM is used (black square), while it increases to 200 nm when a medium with higher ionic strength like PBS is used (red circle). The corresponding data for free NC present a hydrodynamic diameter of approximately 2000 nm when PBS is used (pink triangle), and of 2800 nm when DMEM is used (blue triangle), proving that the encapsulation of the NC significantly improves their colloidal stability. When both NC and NC-NLCs are tested in DMEM + 10% FBS, a similar behavior for both nanoparticles can be observed. This behavior is characterized by a low hydrodynamic diameter, comparable to that one of NC-NLCs in DMEM, and can be attributed to the proteins of FBS that provide an enhanced colloidal stability to the nanoparticles. For a more detailed analysis of NC-NLCs stability please see Figure S1 and S2 (Supporting Information).

Antioxidant Properties. To assess NC-NLCs antioxidant properties, we focused our attention on the •OH scavenging ability of the nanostructures. Among the reactive oxygen species, •OH radical is known to be the most biologically active free radical, damaging DNA and initiating lipid peroxidation,²² and it is involved in numerous cellular disorders such as inflammation, embryo teratogenesis, cell death, and imbalances in phagocytosis.²³ The hydroxyl radicals measured by EPR were generated in situ by a Fenton

Figure 4. Viability studies performed on the three different cellular components of the BBB model (bEnd.3, C8-D1A and differentiated SH-SY5Y) for 24 and 72 h, using plain NLCs (333 and 666 µg/mL), free NC (100 and 200 µg/mL), and NC-NLCs (333 and 666 µg/mL). (a) and (b) bEnd.3 cells, (c) and (d) C8-D1A cells, (e) and (f) differentiated SH-SY5Y cells at 24 h (a, c, e) and 72 h (b, d, f) of treatment, respectively.

chemistry reaction ($\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+} + \cdot\text{OH} + \text{HO}^-$), which is widely used in antioxidant assays,^{24,25} and it was chosen due to its high $\cdot\text{OH}$ radical generation efficiency and reproducibility. Since the hydroxyl radical is a highly reactive chemical species with a very short half-life in the order of nanoseconds,²⁶ its selective detection is only possible via the spin trap technique on EPR.

The results presented in Figure 3a demonstrate that the addition of NC protected the spin trap DMPO from oxidation, and that NC markedly decreased the DMPO–OH spin adduct by scavenging Fenton-generated $\cdot\text{OH}$ (corresponding concentration for each spectrum: NLCs 3.332 mg/mL, NC 1.000 mg/mL, NC-NLCs 3.332 mg/mL). The results in Figure 3b demonstrate how this effect was concentration-dependent over the range of 125 µg/mL–1 mg/mL, reaching 73% of $\cdot\text{OH}$ scavenging efficiency for the highest NC concentration. To understand whether NC preserved their $\cdot\text{OH}$ scavenging

ability once encapsulated in NLCs, NC-NLCs with the equivalent content of NC were assessed. NC-NLCs effectively protected DMPO from oxidation, and this effect was again concentration-dependent up to 65% of $\cdot\text{OH}$ scavenging efficiency for an NC-NLC concentration of 3.33 mg/mL. To distinguish the contribution of the $\cdot\text{OH}$ scavenging ability between NC and NLCs, empty NLCs were also investigated. It is well-known that $\cdot\text{OH}$ can oxidize unsaturated fatty acids in lipid membranes, therefore the latter acting as $\cdot\text{OH}$ scavengers. As shown in Figure 3b, the $\cdot\text{OH}$ scavenging ability of empty NLCs did not exceed 17% of the maximum concentration used. These analyses confirm that the encapsulation of NC inside of NLCs does not affect their antioxidant properties, and these results confirm that the presented NC-NLCs could be used as an innovative lipid-based antioxidant nanovector.

Cell Proliferation Studies. As briefly described in the introduction, NC have raised several concerns regarding their

biocompatibility;²⁷ thus we considered of pivotal importance to perform preliminary *in vitro* studies in order to assess the biocompatibility of NC-NLCs before their use for any biomedical applications. The effect of NC-NLCs on cell viability was tested on three cell lines of the different BBB component of our model that are normally affected by overproduction of ROS: endothelial cells (bEnd.3), astrocytes (C8-D1A), and neurons (differentiated SH-SY5Y). We treated cells using two concentrations of NLCs and NC-NLCs (333 and 666 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) calculated on the basis of the TGA results (Figure 2a) in order to obtain a dose of encapsulated NC equivalent to that one used in the treatments with free NC (100 and 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). From the PicoGreen dsDNA results that are presented in Figure 4, no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in terms of double-strand DNA (dsDNA) quantity was observed between treated and untreated cells either at 24 or 72 h. dsDNA represents an indirect measurement of the number of cells and can be used as an indicator for the evaluation of cell proliferation.²⁸ These results suggest the absence of negative effects on cell viability of free NC, plain NLCs, and NC-NLCs.

Crossing of BBB and Internalization Studies. As previously mentioned, the presence of the BBB is one of the major obstacles for the treatment of neurological diseases, since it is able to prevent the passage of 98% of small therapeutic molecules, and nearly 100% of large molecules, such as monoclonal antibodies (mAbs), recombinant proteins, and gene-based therapeutics.²⁹ To test the ability of NC-NLCs to reach the brain we setup an *in vitro* BBB model as previously described (Figure 5a). Our decision to exploit a triple-culture model rather than a single endothelial cell layer system was driven by the need to generate a system capable of mimicking as faithfully as possible the *in vivo* BBB environment; in fact, it has been widely demonstrated how the direct coculture of BBB cellular components, like astrocytes alongside with brain endothelial cells, is able to enhance both TEER values³⁰ and expression of specific proteins like the P-glycoprotein (P-gp), granting a more restrictive and physiologically relevant model through a significant reduction in paracellular transport of model compounds in comparison with monoculture and with indirect coculture.³⁰ The TEER values reported at the fifth day of culture for our system (TEER = 70 $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$) are comparable with the results described in the literature obtained with the same endothelial cell line, being higher than reported values for single bEnd.3 cultures (around 30 $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$),³¹ and similar to other coculture systems like bEnd.3/C6³² (TEER = 80 $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$). Moreover, we were able to demonstrate through confocal microscopy analysis the expression of the ZO-1 protein by bEnd.3 cells (Figure 5b), specifically localized in the cell-to-cell contact regions, suggesting the formation of tight junction structures.³³ 3D rendering images of our model showed the formation of a bEnd.3 confluent layer on the apical side of the transwell insert, and the presence of C8-D1A cells attached face-down to the basal side (Figure 5c). Lastly, to confirm the successful maturation of the *in vitro* BBB model, we checked the passage of two different fluorescent tracers (FITC-dextran 4 kDa and 70 kDa) from the apical side to the basal side of the transwell insert. As shown in Figure 5d,e, the presence of the bEnd.3/C8-D1A bilayer caused a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in the passage of the two fluorescent compounds, indicating the formation of a barrier. In particular, we observed a statistically significant reduction of fluorescent tracers in the

Figure 5. (a) Schematic representation of the cellular organization and compartmentalization of the fabricated triple-culture system; (b) confocal imaging showing the localized expression of the ZO-1 protein by bEnd.3 cells (ZO-1 in green and nuclei in blue); (c) 3D rendered confocal image showing the formation of a continuous bilayer of cells in correspondence of the porous membrane, with bEnd.3 on the top side and C8-D1A on the bottom side (ZO-1 in green, β -actin in red, nuclei in blue); fluorescence values of (d) 4 kDa and (e) 70 kDa FITC-dextran after their diffusion through a transwell insert with and without cells (* $p < 0.05$).

basolateral side of the transwell insert at 60 min (120 837 \pm 7589 au in control inserts compared to 69 226 \pm 738 au with cells in the case of dextran 4 kDa, and 61408 \pm 3321 au in control inserts compared to 29 920 \pm 3543 with cells in the case of dextran 70 kDa) and at 120 min (225 460 \pm 5629 au in control inserts compared to 162 080 \pm 3847 au with cells in the case of dextran 4 kDa, and 145 365 \pm 1506 au in control inserts compared to 52 697 \pm 2121 au with cells in the case of dextran 70 kDa).

Once the full characterization of the system was carried out, transport and internalization studies have been performed in order to assess the NC-NLC ability to cross the BBB model. We treated the apical side of the BBB model with different concentrations of FITC-NC-NLCs (0.65, 1.3, and 2.6 mg/mL), and we checked the number of particles able to cross the endothelial/astrocytes double layer by measuring the fluorescence intensity of the media in the basolateral compartment of the transwell insert. The analysis revealed that a maximum of 30% and 37% of the particles suspended in the apical side of transwell inserts were able to cross the BBB system at 24 and

Figure 6. FITC-NC-NLCs interaction with a triple-culture BBB in vitro model. (a) 3D confocal rendering showing the FITC-NC-NLC uptake by bEnd.3, C8-D1A, and differentiated SH-SY5Y cells; (b) subcellular localization of the FITC-NC-NLCs inside both bEnd.3 and differentiated SH-SY5Y cells (f-actin in red, FITC-NC-NLCs in green, lysosomes in white, nuclei in blue).

72 h, respectively. The ability of NC-NLCs to be internalized by bEnd.3/C8-D1A and to reach the differentiated SH-SY5Y cells seeded on the basolateral bottom part of the BBB system was confirmed by confocal imaging (Figure 6a) and flow cytometry analysis (Figure S3, Supporting Information). Collectively, all these data demonstrate that the nanoformulation is not only able to be uptaken by the brain endothelial cells of the BBB model, but it is also capable to reach and be internalized by neurons. In addition, it has to be noted that the NC-NLC crossing was achieved at relatively high concentrations, as previously mentioned (maximum quantity reached 0.96 mg/mL of NC-NLCs, equivalent to 0.28 mg/mL of NC).

We further analyzed the internalization process of FITC-NC-NLCs by investigating their intracellular localization through the use of LysoTracker, a dye specifically designed to mark acidic subcellular compartments. The analysis was carried out on both bEnd.3 and differentiated SH-SY5Y, treated for 72 h with FITC-NC-NLCs, and showed no statistically significant internalization of the particles inside lysosomes, with a Pearson's correlation $r = 0.32$ in the case of bEnd.3 and $r = 0.37$ for SH-SY5Y (Figure 6b). As previously mentioned, the subcellular localization of NC has been shown to greatly affect the cells by being able to elicit an antioxidant and cell protective action when internalized in nonacidic intracellular compartments, in contrast to a toxic and pro-oxidative effect when localized inside acidic organelles like lysosomes.³⁴ The

Figure 7. Neuroprotective effect of NC and NC-NLCs on neuronal cells. (a) flow cytometry plots showing values of both ROS-positive and necrotic cells; (b) percentage of necrotic, ROS-positive, and viable cells for each treatment with and without the TBH insult. (* $p < 0.05$).

Pearson's correlation factors suggest that the majority of NC-NLCs are not internalized inside lysosomes where they could be exposed to intracellular acidic pH that could affect their antioxidant abilities. This, along with the aforementioned results that demonstrate the ability of the NC-NLCs to cross the BBB, poses the basis for the exploitation of the presented system in the targeted delivery of nanoantioxidants to the central nervous system.

Neuroprotective and Neurogenic Properties of NC-NLCs. As previously described, most neurological diseases are characterized by neuronal loss and a high level of oxidative

stress. NC have been shown to be able to ameliorate oxidative stress both in vitro³⁵ and in vivo,³⁶ even proving a protective effect against harmful pro-oxidative stimuli. Even more interesting is the reported ability of NC to stimulate both neuronal differentiation and neurite growth, granting them the possibility to be exploited not only as a neuroprotective agent, yet also in regenerative medicine approaches.^{37–39} Taking these data into consideration, we investigated whether NC maintained their neuroprotective and pro-neurogenic properties after the encapsulation inside NLCs. We decided to work using a concentration of NC equal to 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ not only

Figure 8. Analysis of the neurogenic effects of NC-NLCs. (a) 3D confocal rendering showing differentiated SH-SY5Y cells after the treatment with plain NLCs, free NC, and NC-NLCs (β 3-tubulin in green, f-actin in red, nuclei in blue); (b) bright field image of Coomassie Brilliant Blue stained neuronal cells, showing the qualitative increment of neurites after the treatment with NC and NC-NLCs; comparison of (c) neurite/cell ratio and (d) neurite length after treatment with plain NLCs, free NC, or NC-NLCs (* $p < 0.05$).

because it has been shown to be a high-enough quantity to elicit the aforementioned protective and pro-differentiation actions, but also because we already showed that NLCs are able to transport even higher concentration of NC across our BBB model. As shown in Figure 7a and Figure 7b, the treatment with TBH is able to increase the level of intracellular ROS and to induce cell death in positive control cultures. Cells preincubated with plain NLCs showed a statistically significant ($p < 0.5$) reduction in the level of ROS and dead cells, when treated with TBH 1 mM, showing a mild protective effect that was completely absent in the case of cells that were treated with 5 mM of TBH. On the other hand, NC and NC-NLCs demonstrated a strong neuroprotective action, by providing a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction of both intracellular ROS and of cell death levels in neurons treated with both 1 mM and 5 mM of TBH, with respect to controls and to cells treated only with plain NLCs. Control ROS-positive cells percentages were 39.0% and 58.0% after the 1 mM and 5 mM TBH treatment, respectively; in the case of incubation with NLCs the ROS-positive cells percentage drops to 17.5% with 1 mM of TBH, but increased again to 76.0% with 5 mM of TBH; finally, ROS-positive cells percentage in the case of the

treatment with NC are equal to 7.4% and 10.4% following 1 and 5 mM of TBH treatment, respectively, and are equal to 8.0% and 9.6% with the incubation with NC-NLCs, following the 1 mM and 5 mM TBH treatment. We did not observe any significant difference in terms of necrotic cells preincubated with NC-NLC with respect to the NC group after the 1 mM TBH treatment; instead, a small yet significant increase of necrotic cells between these two experimental groups was observed after the 5 mM TBH treatment. This difference can be probably attributed to the fact that the scavenging ability of the encapsulated nanoceria is slightly lower with respect to the free NC, as it can be observed from the results presented in Figure 3b. However, we would like to emphasize the fact that, even though we observed this difference in the NC and NC-NLC experimental groups, necrotic and ROS-positive cells detected in the control cultures after the 5 mM TBH treatment (93.3%) are remarkably higher with respect to both the NC (15.4%) and the NC-NLCs (22.8%) experimental conditions, demonstrating a strong protective effect. These data are confirming EPR analysis results, showing both that NLCs have a mild antioxidant effect, and that NC and NC-NLCs elicit an equivalent strong ROS scavenging action.

Finally, we checked the effect of NC-NLCs on the neuronal differentiation of SH-SY5Y cells (Figure 8). After 3 days of incubation with plain NLCs (333 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, Figure 8a), we did not observe any statistically significant difference in terms of neurite average length and numbers with respect to the untreated group. However, we observed a statistically significant increment in neurite numbers (with an increment of $62.3\% \pm 11.2\%$ in the case of treatment with NC and of $66.1\% \pm 11.4\%$ in the case of treatment with NC-NLCs; Figure 8b) and neurite average length (with an increment of the median values from $43.0 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{m}$ to $61.8 \pm 3.6 \mu\text{m}$ in the case of treatment with NC and to $73.7 \pm 3.6 \mu\text{m}$ with the treatment with NC-NLCs; Figure 8c) in neurons treated with NC (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and NC-NLCs (333 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), while we did not observe a statistically significant difference between the latter two treatments. This enhancement of the differentiation process could be caused by the antioxidant effect of NC as already described in the literature,^{37,39} and altogether these results demonstrate not only that NC-NLCs are able to protect neurons from pro-oxidative stress, but also that they are capable of enhancing the differentiation of neuronal cells, thus opening new exciting possibilities of applications in the treatment of brain disorders.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we demonstrated for the first time the preparation of a lipid-based delivery system able to encapsulate antioxidant NC and to cross a triple-culture in vitro BBB model. We were able to largely improve the colloidal stability of NC, while not affecting their antioxidant ability. Moreover, we demonstrated the capacity of our nanovectors to be internalized by neurons and to act both as a neuroprotective and pro-neurogenic agent. All these results lay the base for further investigations of our nanoplatform in vitro as well as in vivo, with the aim to provide new data for a realistic future clinical exploitation of cerium oxide nanoparticles in a broad spectrum of applications, ranging from the treatment of neurological diseases to innovative approaches against brain cancer.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: [10.1021/acsbomaterials.8b01033](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbomaterials.8b01033).

Size and correlation coefficient graphs showing DLS stability studies in different media of NC and NC-NLCs at different time points; flow cytometry data confirming NC-NLCs BBB crossing ability (PDF)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

*E-mail: matteo.battaglini@iit.it.

*E-mail: christos.tapeinos@iit.it.

*E-mail: gianni.ciofani@iit.it.

ORCID

Valentina Cauda: [0000-0003-2382-1533](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2382-1533)

Gianni Ciofani: [0000-0003-1192-3647](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1192-3647)

Author Contributions

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Notes

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